

Volume Optimization for a Given End-Shape Family: Using Short End-Shaped Ductile Fibers to Improve the Fracture Toughness of a Brittle Composite

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Abstract

Short end-shaped copper fibers were added to improve the fracture toughness of a brittle epoxy matrix composite. Shaping the ends of the fiber allows anchoring of the fiber into the matrix. Once debonded, the shaped fiber head anchors the fiber in the matrix, resulting in high utilization of the plastic work potential of the fiber. To pull out of the matrix, the fiber can: plastically deform and fail along the fiber shaft, deform the fiber ends enough to pull out of the matrix, pull the fiber through by fracturing the matrix, or a combination of these three failure mechanisms. These failure mechanisms take advantage of the plastic work potential of the fiber volume and result in a significant increase in fracture toughening when compared to a straight end fiber. Two fiber end-shape families were investigated: flat end and rippled and compared against an axisymmetric end-shape to determine which performed better. Using single fiber pullout tests, we determined that for a given family of end-shapes there is an optimum volume; above or below this volume results in lower fracture toughness.

We looked at two types of fiber anchoring: single anchoring with the flat end-shape and multiple anchoring with the rippled end-shape. We determined that single anchoring of the fiber into the matrix was more effective than multiple anchoring because the single anchored fiber could pull out of the matrix at deeper embedment depths resulting in higher fracture toughness. When creating the end shape, the fiber end is cold worked; to restore the fiber ductility the fibers were annealed. We determined that annealing had no significant impact on the fracture toughness. This indicates that the dependence of the overall fiber contribution on the plasticity of the fiber end is small. Because a crack plane can intersect a fiber at any angle, the effects of angle embedment were tested using the medium flat end, which was the best fiber end candidate at 0° embedment angle. The medium flat end fiber performed better than the straight cut fiber end at embedment angles up to 30°, while the straight cut fiber outperforms the flat end fiber at angles above 30. The net effect is still a significant improvement in fracture toughness because the higher angle fibers have a relatively small probability of crossing the crack plane. Preliminary results from four-point bending tests indicate that the use of ductile fibers significantly increases the fracture work of a composite beam. The addition of 5 volume percent of 10mm long straight cut fibers to the epoxy matrix dramatically increased the work to fracture the beam, 1010% versus a beam with no fibers. Future work will include the addition of 5 volume percent of flat end-shaped fibers to determine if the end-shaped fibers offer as dramatic an increase in the fracture toughness of the composite.

Keywords: Fracture toughening; Shaped ductile fibers

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Symbols:

δ = Crack opening distance

$\delta(\psi)$ = Dirac delta function

ψ = Angle that a fiber crosses the crack plane

A_c = Cross sectional area of the composite

$g(l_e, \psi)$ = Energy absorbed by single fiber during pullout

ΔG = Fracture toughness increment

l_e = Embedded fiber length

v_f = Fiber volume fraction

Introduction

Short ductile fibers can be added to a brittle matrix to inhibit crack initiation and propagation of the crack. Straight ductile fibers were considered by Bowling and Groves who modeled the pull out of a yielding ductile fiber [1,2]. Their research illustrated the competition between pull out and yielding. When a crack develops in the composite, straight fibers debond at the crack face and bridge the crack. As the fiber is pulled, the fiber will continue to debond and if suitably embedded may start to plastically deform. During plastic yielding the diameter of the fiber is reduced and the interfacial shear stress is reduced and can go to zero at the debonded surface, assuming poor bonding. As more of the fiber is plastically deformed, the debonding stress required to pull out the fiber becomes less than the force required to continue fiber hardening, so the final plug pulls out. This leaves a section of the fiber that does not contribute to the pullout work and constitutes a waste of plastic potential. Wetherhold and Bös conducted experiments with ductile fibers in an epoxy matrix to demonstrate the amount of plastic work potential in a ductile fiber and how that ductility could be utilized by anchoring the fiber into the matrix [3]. Anchoring of the fiber end could increase the fracture toughness of the composite by preventing fiber pullout. The amount of work to plastically deform the length of the fiber up to the plug and then breaking off the plug and pulling the remainder out is much higher than the work required to pull out a straight fiber. When using a straight ductile fiber, a high interface shear stress is desirable to combine frictional pullout work with plastic deformation of the fiber, which increases the pullout work and the toughness of the composite. When using shaped ductile fibers in a composite, the interface shear stress contribution is less important because the pullout work is based predominantly on the fiber plasticity.

Fiber End Shape Family: The amount of improvement seen in the fracture toughness is closely related to the fiber end geometry. To maximize the pullout work of a shaped fiber end, the desired failure modes are: pullout of the fiber by large deformation of the shaped ends, pull out of the fiber end by tearing out the matrix, and to a lesser extent the fracture of the fiber and pullout of the fractured fiber. If the shape of the fiber end anchors the fiber too firmly into the matrix and is unable to break through the matrix, then the fiber will quickly reach its ultimate strength and fail. This can result in pullout energies that are lower than that for the straight fiber end. If the size of the fiber end is too small, not significantly larger than the fiber itself, then the fiber end can pull out of the matrix without significant plastic deformation of the fiber shaft. At shallow embedment depths, usually below 2.5mm, the better the fiber is anchored the higher is the pullout work. This is because the fiber end can break through the matrix before the ultimate strength

Figure 1: Comparison of pullout work between axisymmetric lightly end impacted and fully end impacted fibers.

of the fiber is reached. At deeper embedment depths, the geometry of the fiber end shape family is more important for reasons stated above. Recent work by Wetherhold and Lee demonstrates the importance of fiber end shape family geometry and embedment depth on the pullout work [4]. Using low ductility copper fibers in a low shrinkage epoxy, a large axisymmetric end (3D fully impacted fiber end) was compared with a light axisymmetric end (3D lightly impacted fiber end). The fully impacted fiber end performed better than the lightly impacted fiber end at lower embedment depths, but performed poorer than the straight cut and lightly impacted end at higher embedment depths, see Figure 1. The results demonstrate the difficulties in determining the optimum fiber end shape family.

The goals of this research were to find a flat end impacted fiber geometry that is easier to produce and further improves the fracture toughness increment over that of an axisymmetric end impacted fiber. We will also determine the effects of annealing cold worked fiber ends to determine if restoring the ductility of the fiber end improves the pullout work. Since an oxide coating forms on the fiber during annealing, this coating was removed to determine if the removal of the oxide affects the pullout work of the annealed fiber end. The effect of multiple mechanical interlocking was investigated to determine if this interlocking is more effective than single anchoring of the fiber end.

Experimental Procedure

Pullout work was determined through single fiber pullout tests. Straight and end shaped fibers were embedded at varying depths in epoxy and pulled out once the epoxy had cured for 48 hours. The setup for single fiber pullout tests is based on work done by Piggot and Dai [5]. Copper foil was glued to the free end of the copper wire with a 3mm free length to accommodate the shear plates that were used to restrain the sample during pull-out tests; see Figure 2. Fibers that were embedded at an angle into the epoxy were gently straightened before gluing to the copper foil. The fibers were pulled out of the epoxy using a Sintech 2D test machine with a 100lb load cell and a crosshead speed of 1mm/min.

Fiber end size	Length-L (mm)	Width-W (mm)	Thick-T (mm)	L / D
Small	0.44	0.38	0.26	1.38
Medium	0.87	0.38	0.29	2.72
Large	2.07	0.50	0.26	6.47

Table 1: Average dimensions for the three flat end impacted fibers (D is the diameter of the wire); see Figure 3.

mixed by weight in the ratio of 100 parts resin to 30 parts catalyst. A 5ml plastic pipette was filled with the mixed epoxy to control the flow of the epoxy into 0.30 ml sample cups.

Fiber Preparation: All specimens were prepared using 80mm long pieces of wire that were cut with a razor blade to ensure a straight flat cut. The diameter of the copper wire was 0.32mm, the yield strength was 170MPa, and the ultimate tensile strength was 223MPa. The wires were gently straightened by hand and the ends examined to ensure they were not overly deformed when cut. To produce flat end impacted fibers, a piece of wire was inserted into a capillary tube and the tube was inserted into the impact fixture and impacted. The resulting specimen was measured and if necessary the distance between the two impact surfaces were adjusted to achieve to desired dimensions. Table 1 tabulates the average dimensions of the fiber end for the three sizes used for the experiments.

Medium flat end impacted fibers were annealed to determine the effects of cold working of the fiber end on the pullout work. The temperature where atomic mobility is sufficient to affect the microstructure and cause recrystallization is approximately 1/3 to 1/2 the absolute melting point (T_m) of the metal. For

Figure 2: Schematics of completed specimens for (a) vertical and (b) angled embedment.

Materials: The epoxy used for the experiments was a room temperature cure Bisphenol-A Epichlorohydrin based epoxy resin with an aliphatic polyamine catalyst with a gel time of approximately 30 to 45 minutes. The epoxy $\sigma_U = 64.8$ MPa and the cure shrinkage = 0.006 in/in. The epoxy had optical clarity to allow observation of fiber embedment and pullout. The epoxy was

copper, this is between 180°C and 405°C [6]. The fibers were placed into an annealing furnace set at 275°C for five minutes then removed from the furnace and air-cooled. To test the effect of the oxide coating on the surface of the annealed fibers the oxide was removed with a 5% solution of H₂SO₄ and immediately tested.

Fiber end type	'A' (mm)	'P' (mm)	'W' (mm)	'A'/D	'P'/D	'W'/D
Light Ripple	0.049	0.80	0.30	0.15	2.50	0.94
Heavy Ripple	0.025	0.80	0.33	0.08	2.50	1.03

Table 2: Average dimensions for rippled fiber ends.

To produce a rippled fiber end, an 80mm length of wire was placed in between two jaws that close flat against each other and squeezed to achieve the desired shape. Table 2 is the average dimensions for the heavy and light rippled fiber end used for the experiments, where A is the amplitude, P is the period, and W is the width.

Beam Preparation and Testing: To make a composite beam, 3.7% by weight silica was added to increase the viscosity of the epoxy to prevent fiber settling during cure; $\rho_{Cu} = 8.93 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho_{Epoxy} = 1.10 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho_{Silica} = 0.06 \text{ g/cm}^3$. The epoxy was mixed by weight in the ratio of 100 parts resin to 30 parts catalyst to 5 parts amorphous silica. The epoxy was poured into a silicon rubber mold and the beams were cured for 48 hours, then the specimens were tested in four point bend until failure. The beams were unnotched with the following dimensions: 10mm wide x 10mm high x 100mm long. The beams were tested in flexure using a four-point bend fixture with a span of 80mm and a center span of 40mm. A 2000lb load cell was used with a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min.

To increase the work required to fracture the beam specimen, 5 vol% straight cut fibers were added to the mixed silica epoxy. Two lengths of fibers were added to the silica epoxy to determine the effects of fiber length on the work required to fracture the beam specimen: 7mm and 10mm long fibers. The epoxy was prepared as stated previously. The cut fibers were cleaned in alcohol and completely dried. The cleaned fibers were then added to the mixed epoxy and gently stirred. Once all the fibers were mixed into the epoxy, the epoxy was poured into the mold. A spatula was used to ensure an even distribution of aligned fibers in the specimen and any large trapped air bubbles were removed with a syringe. After 48 hours of room temperature cure, the specimens were tested in flexure until failure. The same procedure was used for the 7mm and the 10mm long fibers. 5 samples of each fiber length were prepared to determine the average work to fracture the composite beam. The results of the unreinforced beam specimens were compared with those for the two fiber lengths of the composite specimens.

Experimental Results

The predicted fracture toughness increment was calculated for all the fiber ends used and assumes $l_f = 10\text{mm}$ and $v_f = 0.20$. The shaped fiber ends were compared to the straight cut fiber ends to determine the highest performing fiber shape examined in this research. The comparison of fracture toughness increment of the shaped fiber end to the straight cut fiber end is represented as $(\Delta G/\Delta G^*)$ in the tables, where ΔG is the calculated fracture toughness increment for the various fiber ends and ΔG^* is the fracture toughness increment for the straight fiber. The 0° embedded fibers were fitted to the data points using a least squares method in the form $W = a l_e + b l_e^2 + c l_e^3$. The angular embedded fibers were fitted to the data points using a least squares method in the form $W = a l_e + b \psi + c l_e^2 + d \psi^2$. The fitted curves were used in the fracture toughness increment predictions, $g(l_e, \psi)$. Equation 1 was used to determine the composite fracture energy increment and is based on work by Wetherhold and Jain [7,8,9]. The single fiber pullout experiments were performed for ψ from 0 to $\pi/4$ and l_e from 1.5mm. Below 1.5mm the pullout energy was set to zero because the pullout energy was assumed to be very low.

$$\Delta G = \frac{v_f}{A_c} \int_{\psi=0}^{\frac{\pi}{4}} \int_{l_c=1.5}^{\left(\frac{l_f}{2}\right)} g(l_c, \psi) \left(\frac{2}{l_f}\right) f_\psi(\psi) \sin \psi \cos \psi dl_c d\psi \quad (1)$$

Effect of Fiber End Volume: The flat end shape family had three sizes: small, medium, and large having an L/D ratio corresponding to 1.38, 2.72, and 6.47 and were embedded at a 0° angle and tested. The results of each size were compared to determine if there was an optimum size for a chosen end shape family. The results show that for the same end shape family there was an optimum volume; above this volume the performance of the fiber decreases. The large flat end impacted fiber fractured through the matrix at low embedment depths, at deeper embedment depths the large end fails in the matrix resulting in lower work because of the loss of frictional work and plastic utilization of the volume of the embedded fiber end. For the flat impacted fiber end, the small and medium size end can deform and pull out of the matrix.

Figure 3: Comparison of pullout work for the three flat end impacted fiber sizes and the straight cut fiber end, 0° degree embedment angle.

The medium sized end plastically deforms more than the smaller size end resulting in a better performance. The flat impacted ends were compared to the straight fiber in Figure 3; the small and medium size ends perform better than the straight fiber end, the large end has a lower pullout work curve than the straight fiber end. Figure 3 further shows that when the fibers were able to pull out of the matrix, the pullout work increases with increasing embedment depth. When the fibers reach an embedment depth where either all or some of the fibers fail in the matrix, the pull-out curve starts to level off and reach a plateau as more fibers fail in the matrix at deeper embedment depths. Table 3 tabulates the predicted fracture toughness increment for the flat impacted fibers and the straight cut fiber.

Fiber End Geometry	Fiber Orientation	ΔG [KJ/m ²]	$\Delta G/\Delta G^*$
Straight	Unidirectional - 0°	36.4 (ΔG^*)	1.00
Flat Small End Impacted	Unidirectional - 0°	45.0	1.24
Medium Flat End Impacted	Unidirectional - 0°	53.1	1.46
Large Flat End Impacted	Unidirectional - 0°	34.8	0.96

Table 3: Predicted fracture toughness for flat end impacted fibers and straight cut fiber ends.

Effect of Multiple Mechanical Interlocking:

At embedment depths up to 3.5mm all the rippled fibers tested were able to pull out of the matrix, above 3.5mm either most or all of the fibers fail in the epoxy matrix. Figure 4 shows the load versus displacement curves for a lightly rippled fiber embedded at a depth of 4.0mm and 4.5mm at 0° embedment angle. The period of the ripples was 0.80mm and this distance corresponds to the distance between the peaks in the Load – Displacement curve. The figure shows that the deeper the embedment depth, the more the fiber initially plastically deforms before debonding.

Figure 4: Load – Displacement curves for a lightly rippled fiber demonstrating the “speed bump” effect, 0° embedment angle, A = 0.025mm, P = 0.80mm.

Two fiber amplitudes were investigated; a heavily rippled fiber (A=0.049mm, P=0.80mm) and a lightly rippled fiber (A=0.025mm, P=0.80mm). We define the median critical embedment depth to be the depth where half of the fibers fail rather than pull out because above this embedment depth most or all of the fibers fail. The lightly rippled fiber had a critical embedment depth of 3.5mm and the heavy rippled fiber had a critical embedment depth of 3.0mm. This critical embedment depth can be seen in Figure 5; for the heavy rippled fiber end the pullout work curve starts to plateau after 3.0mm because more of the fibers fail in the matrix. The pullout work curve for the lightly rippled fiber end keeps increasing because the number of fibers failing in the matrix does not increase until an embedment depth of 5.0mm is reached; thereafter, a drop in the pullout work curve was observed. Table 4 compares the predicted fracture toughness increment between the light and heavy rippled fiber. The lightly rippled fiber end performed better than the heavy rippled fiber end because more of the lightly rippled fibers pulled out at deeper embedment depths. The lightly rippled fiber end performed slightly better than the straight cut fiber end because the fibers that pulled out at deeper embedment depths had higher pullout work.

Figure 5: Comparison of the work of pullout for a heavy and lightly rippled fiber end, 0° embedment angle.

Fiber End Geometry	Fiber Orientation	ΔG [KJ/m ²]	$\Delta G / \Delta G^*$
Light Ripple	Unidirectional - 0°	38.3	1.05
Heavy Ripple	Unidirectional - 0°	30.0	0.82

Table 4: Predicted fracture toughness increment for light and heavy rippled fibers.

Effects of Annealing and Surface Preparation (Oxide Removal): The effects of annealing and the resulting oxide coating were investigated using the large flat end impacted fibers. When impacted, the fiber end was cold worked, which increases its yield and lowers its ductility. The results show that annealing and oxide removal had no significant affect on the fracture toughness contribution of the fiber, see Figure 6. However, a moderate decrease in the average debonding force was seen: 1.0% to 11% for the as-annealed fibers and 3.4% to 23.5% for annealed fibers with the oxide removed, depending on the embedment depth. This indicates that annealing slightly weakens the fiber-matrix bond and that the oxide removal further reduces this bond; see Table 5. Table 6 shows the predicted fracture toughness increment for the fibers for 0° orientation. All three of the fiber ends had a lower fracture toughness increment compared to the straight cut fiber end. To determine the effectiveness of the annealing of the impacted fibers, annealed fibers were compared visually to unannealed fibers using polished samples and an optical microscope. The grains of the unannealed fibers were elongated and flattened, typical of cold worked grains. The grains for the annealed fiber were of similar size to that of the straight cut fiber, indicating that the annealing time and temperature were effective in recovering the grain structure.

Embedment Depth (mm)	Flat Large As Impacted	Flat Large As Annealed	Flat Large – Annealed and Oxide Removed
1.5	9.8 ± 3.7	9.0 ± 1.9	7.5 ± 1.9
2.0	14.5 ± 2.8	12.9 ± 2.9	12.1 ± 1.4
2.5	17.4 ± 0.3	17.2 ± 1.0	16.8 ± 1.4
3.0	18.4 ± 1.3	16.9 ± 1.7	16.4 ± 1.7

Table 5: Debond Force (N): flat Large as impacted, as annealed, and annealed with the oxide removed.

Figure 6: Comparison of the pullout work for the large flat end impacted fiber as-impacted, annealed, and annealed with the oxide coating removed, 0° embedment angle.

Fiber End Geometry	Fiber Orientation	ΔG [KJ/m ²]	$\Delta G/\Delta G^*$
Flat Large As Impacted	Unidirectional - 0°	34.8	0.96
Flat Large As Annealed	Unidirectional - 0°	35.6	0.98
Flat Large Annealed, Oxide Removed	Unidirectional - 0°	35.0	0.96

Table 6: Predicted Fracture toughness increment for the flat large end impacted fibers: as impacted, as-annealed, and annealed with the oxide coating removed.

Effects of Fiber Embedment Angle:

Because a crack plane can intersect a fiber at any angle, the effects of angle embedment were tested. The medium flat end impacted fiber was chosen for angle embedment because it performed the best of all the ends studied for aligned fiber orientation. The medium flat fibers were embedded at 0°, 15°, 30° and 45° angles. Table 8 shows that for a random fiber orientation between 0° and 45° the calculated fracture toughness increment for medium flat end impacted fibers was 59% higher than for randomly oriented straight cut fibers. The table further shows that the randomly oriented fibers have a lower fracture toughness increment than the unidirectional oriented fibers. This is a net effect because while the higher angle embedded fibers produce lower work but also have less importance because they have a smaller chance of intersecting a crack plane. Figure 7 compares the work for straight cut fibers to the medium flat end impacted fiber for various embedment depths and embedment angles. The medium flat end impacted fiber adds more toughness than the straight cut fiber end at lower embedment angles. At embedment angles above 30°, the straight cut fiber end tends to outperform the medium flat end impacted fiber. This was acceptable because low angle embedment results heavily influence the predicted fracture toughness equation because the higher the embedment angle, the lower the probability of the fiber's intersecting the crack plane.

Fiber End Geometry	Fiber Orientation	ΔG [KJ/m ²]	$\Delta G/\Delta G^*$
Straight	Unidirectional - 0°	36.4 (ΔG^*)	1.00
Straight	Random [0,π/4]	32.5	0.89
Medium Flat Impact	Unidirectional - 0°	53.1	1.46
Medium Flat Impact	Random [0,π/4]	51.3	1.41

Table 8: Predicted fracture toughness increment for the straight cut and medium flat end impacted fibers: unidirectional and randomly oriented.

White Grid: Straight Fiber End
Gray Grid: Medium Flat End Impacted

Figure 7: Work versus embedment angle versus embedment depth for straight cut and medium flat end impacted fibers.

Effect of Fiber Length on Fracture Work in Composite Flexure Testing:

Two straight cut fiber lengths, 7mm and 10mm, were added to the matrix to increase the work required to fracture the beam. The fibers were randomly located in the composite with unidirectional orientation. Beams without fibers were compared to beams with 5 vol% of 7mm fibers and 5 vol% of 10mm fibers; see Figure 8. The results show that the addition of fibers significantly increases the work required to fracture the beam, a 790% increase from (461 N-mm ± 182 N-mm) for the 7mm fibers and a 1010% increase from (576 N-mm ± 115 N-mm) for the 10mm fibers when compared against the beams with no fibers. The addition of fibers greatly increases the toughness of the beam as measured from the load – deflection curve. Without fibers the beam fails catastrophically; the addition of the fibers results in

a more ductile type failure. When the crack intersects a fiber, the shorter embedded end pulls out, typically with little deformation of the fiber. This results in little utilization of the fibers' plasticity.

Discussion

Effect of Fiber End Shape Family: For the materials tested by Lee, any shaped fiber end provided higher fracture toughness than that of a straight cut fiber [4]. The results of these current experiments show a larger view. The large flat end impacted and the heavy rippled fiber end provided a lower fracture toughening increment than that of the straight fibers. This means that an arbitrarily end shaped fiber cannot be assumed to perform better than the straight cut fiber.

The results also demonstrate that if the fiber end volume is too large (large flat impacted) and/or the fiber end is mechanically bonded too well (heavy rippled) into the matrix, the performance is decreased. This was because these shaped ends were unable to deform sufficiently to pull out of the matrix and/or distort the matrix enough to pull out. The fiber shaft fails, and the majority of the work was from the plastic deformation of the fiber shaft to failure and the resulting frictional work as the fiber shaft pulls out of the matrix. When the fiber shaft fails, the fiber end was left embedded in the matrix resulting in a lower fracture toughening increment versus a straight fiber. $\Delta G/\Delta G^*$ for the large flat end impacted fibers was 0.96 and for the heavy rippled fiber end was 0.82.

The ΔG values for the medium flat end impacted fiber range from: minimum of 44.9 KJ/m², average of 53.1 KJ/m², and a maximum of 65.2 KJ/m². Lee had a $\Delta G = 54.1$ KJ/m² for an axisymmetric end impacted fiber so the flat end impacted fiber performed as well as the axisymmetric end impacted fiber within experimental error. The advantages of a flat end impacted fiber are their easier and faster production. Hence the flat end impacted fiber geometry is preferable to the axisymmetric end impacted fiber geometry.

Annealing and Surface Preparation: When fiber ends are cold worked to achieve their desired shape, the fiber end becomes harder and less ductile. The fibers were annealed and the results show that there was not a significant increase in the amount of pullout work; this indicates that the loss of plastic potential upon cold working in the fiber end was offset by the increase in strength of the fiber end or that the dependence on the plasticity of the fiber end was small. When the flat end impacted fibers were heat-treated, an oxide coating formed on the surface of the fiber. The oxide coating was removed and the fibers were tested to determine if the fracture toughness increment would be affected. Results showed no significant improvement in the fracture toughness increment for the fibers with the oxide coating removed. However, a moderate decrease in the average debonding force was seen: 1.0% to 11% for the as-annealed fibers and 3.4% to 23.5% for annealed fibers with the oxide removed, depending on the embedment depth. This indicates that annealing weakens the fiber-matrix bond and the oxide removal further reduces this bond. This is useful for tailoring purposes; if the debonding force of a fiber end is higher than the strength of the fiber then annealing could reduce the debonding force below the ultimate

Figure 8: Average Load versus Deflection {4pt bending} – Beam with 5vol% 7mm fibers versus beam with 5vol% 10mm fibers.

strength of the fiber allowing debonding, dependant on the material properties. The friction between the fiber and the matrix was not significantly affected because the overall fracture toughness was unaffected by annealing.

Fiber Addition to Composite Beams: The addition of the straight fibers significantly increases the work required to fracture the beam when compared to a beam without fibers: a 1010% increase was achieved for the 10mm fibers. This demonstrates that the addition of fibers to the matrix at low volume fractions results in a large increase in the fracture toughness of the beam. The fibers prevent the beams from having a catastrophic or brittle type failure. The straight cut fibers do not significantly plastically deform while debonding and then pulling out of the matrix. Therefore, adding end shaped fibers to the matrix should further increase the fracture work and fracture toughness by utilizing more of the fiber plasticity through anchoring of the fibers into the matrix.

Conclusions

Within experimental error, the flat end impacted fiber performs at least as well as the axisymmetric end impacted fiber. The advantages of a flat end impacted fiber are their easier and faster production and so they are preferable to the axisymmetric end impacted fiber geometry for fracture toughening.

Fracture toughness depends on the fiber properties, the fiber end shape family, the friction at the interface, and the matrix properties. There is an optimal volume for a given fiber end shape family and matrix; all shaped fiber ends do not necessarily perform better than a straight cut fiber end. When considering a new fiber end shape family, the effectiveness of the new geometry can be screened by pullout tests before adding these fibers to a composite beam for testing. Annealing a cold worked fiber end does not result in an increase in the pullout work; hence annealing was unnecessary. Removal of the oxide coating does not result in an increase in the pullout work; hence oxide removal was also unnecessary. However, a decrease in the debonding force was seen in the annealed fibers and a further reduction was seen when the oxide was removed, this indicates that annealing and oxide removal weakens the fiber-matrix bond. This is useful for tailoring purposes; if the debonding force of a fiber end is higher than the strength of the fiber, then annealing could reduce the debonding force below the ultimate strength of the fiber allowing debonding, dependent on the material properties. Multiple mechanical interlocking was not necessarily an improvement over single anchoring of the fiber ends, the lightly rippled fiber end performed slightly better than the straight cut fiber. The addition of the straight fibers significantly increases the work required to fracture a beam when compared to a beam without fibers. Future work will include the addition of 5 volume percent of flat end-shaped fibers to determine if the end-shaped fibers offer as dramatic an increase in the fracture toughness of the composite.

References

- [1] Bowling J., Groves G.W., Mater. Sci. 14 (1979) 443.
- [2] Bowling J., Groves G.W., Mater. Sci. 14 (1979) 431.
- [3] Wetherhold R.C., Bös J.H., Theor. App. Frac. Mech. 33 (2000) 83.
- [4] Wetherhold R.C., Lee F.K., Comp. Sci. Tech. 61 (2001) 517.
- [5] Piggott M.R., Dai S.R., Poly. Eng. Sci. 31(17) (1991) 1246.
- [6] American Society for Metals, "Heat treating, cleaning, and finishing," 8th Edition, 2nd Volume, 1964: 284.
- [7] Wetherhold R.C., Jain L.K., Mater. Sci. Eng. A151 (1992) 169.
- [8] Jain L.K., Wetherhold R.C., Acta. Metall. Mater. 40(6) (1992) 1135.
- [9] Wetherhold R.C., Jain L.K., Mater. Sci. Eng. A165(1993)91.